

Influence of Organisational Climate on Leadership: A Quantitative Analysis of the Work Environment Perceptions in Ecuador

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Abstract

Background: A favourable organisational climate, characterised by open communication and supportive leadership, directly impacts academic and administrative performance. Transformational leadership, in particular, promotes motivation, creativity and commitment, while transactional leadership, although useful in certain contexts, does not generate long-term innovation. However, a clear model is needed to explain how organisational climate and leadership interact specifically in educational institutions.

Objective: This study sought to develop a model based on organisational climate that explains leadership's influence on higher education's institutional performance. It considers the dimensions of organisational climate and how they affect different leadership styles.

Methodology: A quantitative approach was used through a descriptive survey. A total of 892 participants, including executives and administrators, were evaluated using the Organisational Climate and Leadership Measurement Instrument “IMCOL” questionnaire, which measures organisational climate and leadership through a Likert scale from 1 to 5. A multiple regression and correlation analysis were applied to evaluate the relationship between the variables.

Results: The results show a moderate positive correlation between organisational climate and leadership (Spearman's Rho = 0.69, $p < 0.001$). Perception of boss-worker communication, reliability of feedback from co-workers, and opportunity to influence superiors were the most relevant predictors of leadership. Transformational leadership significantly improves organisational climate, contributing to professional development and improved academic and administrative performance.

Conclusion: The study concludes that a positive organisational climate reinforces the effectiveness of leadership, especially transformational leadership, promoting more creative and

collaborative work environments. This, in turn, improves academic and administrative results, increasing employee satisfaction and commitment to institutional goals.

Unique contribution: The study develops a model that shows how dimensions of organisational climate, such as effective communication and trust, are key determinants for improving leadership in educational institutions.

Key Recommendation: Higher education institutions should foster a positive organisational climate by developing transformational leadership programmes that promote innovation, motivation and employee engagement to improve institutional performance.

Keywords: organisational climate, transformational leadership, transactional leadership, higher education, innovation, motivation.

Introduction

Organisational climate and leadership have become key aspects in the effective management of institutions, especially in higher education, where the quality of the work environment directly affects academic and administrative performance. The literature has extensively documented the interrelationship between these two variables, highlighting how employees' perception of organisational climate influences how they respond to prevailing leadership styles, and how, in turn, leaders can shape and improve such climate to optimise institutional performance (Ko et al., 2019).

Organizational climate is defined as the set of perceptions shared by the members of an organization regarding their work environment; these perceptions are influenced by various factors, such as organizational policies, the quality of interactions among employees, the level of support received from leaders and professional development opportunities; a positive organizational climate is related to high levels of job satisfaction, intrinsic motivation and greater commitment to institutional goals. Recent studies have highlighted the importance of a healthy work climate in higher education, where collaboration and innovation are key to fostering an effective learning environment (Brito-Carrillo et al., 2020).

In this context, transformational leadership has emerged as one of the most effective styles to positively influence the organisational climate, characterised by inspiring, motivating followers, and fostering a shared vision that promotes the employees' personal and professional development. This leadership style improves employee engagement and contributes to creating an organisational environment that promotes trust, creativity and collaborative problem-solving (Almaqableha & Omar, 2024). A virtue of transformational leaders is establishing relationships of trust and mutual respect with their teams, which reinforces a positive organisational climate and facilitates the achievement of the institution's strategic goals and objectives (Lockstone-Binney et al., 2019).

In the same vein, this type of leadership is based on a system of rewards and sanctions to condition the behavior of employees, it can also have a significant impact on the organizational climate, although with certain limitations being effective the application of leadership style, optionally in environments where clarity in expectations and the fulfillment of immediate objectives are a priority, its ability to foster a motivating and creative work environment is limited compared to transformational leadership. In higher education institutions, where innovation and adaptability are essential, transactional leadership may be useful in specific situations, but it is insufficient to

promote holistic staff development or to enhance long-term organisational cohesion (Ko et al., 2019).

The interaction between organizational climate and leadership is manifested in various ways in higher education institutions, a positive organizational climate favors the effectiveness of leadership, as it provides a solid foundation on which leaders can build productive and effective relationships with their teams; which generates healthy work environments, characterized by equity, access to adequate resources and emotional well-being, facilitates the implementation of transformational leadership practices, which in turn reinforce and further improve the organizational climate (Brito-Carrillo et al., 2020). Likewise, a negative organisational climate, marked by mistrust and a lack of support, can break the effectiveness of leadership, generating a work dynamic that hinders the achievement of institutional objectives and affects the employees' well-being (Almaqableha & Omar, 2024).

In this sense, effective management of organisational climate and leadership in higher education institutions requires a deep understanding of the dimensions that influence these variables. Open communication, performance recognition, and professional development opportunities are essential to improving organisational climate and increasing leadership effectiveness. According to previous research, well-implemented transformational leadership, combined with a positive organisational climate, can lead to substantial improvements in staff performance and satisfaction, as well as in the educational and administrative quality of the institution (Lockstone-Binney et al., 2019).

The present study aims to quantitatively analyse the relationship between organisational climate and leadership in a higher education institution, to identify the dimensions of climate that influence leadership styles. This research will seek to provide a detailed analysis of how perceptions of the work environment affect leadership effectiveness and propose strategies to improve the organisational climate. By improving the work environment, it is hoped that institutions can increase not only the satisfaction and performance of their employees but also the quality of their management and academic outcomes.

Methodology

For the following study, a quantitative approach was applied, which has as its main objective to quantify the data and in turn the application of psychometric instruments to evaluate the variables of leadership and organizational climate, cross-sectional type cut, which refers to the collection of data in a single moment of time, descriptive type, based on describing the characteristics of the sample; the correlation that allows relating the variables to each other (Hernández Sampier & Mendoza Torres, 2018).

Participants

The study had a sample of 892 subjects, made up of executives and administrators of an institution of higher education, distributed as follows, according to their gender: 442 females with the equivalent (49,6%) and 450 males with the equivalent (50,4%). Thus, the sample applied in this research study is non-probabilistic, by convenience; it indicates fundamental characteristics in the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Instruments

The IMCOL questionnaire by Mellano (2005) was applied. The purpose of the questionnaire was to evaluate the organisational climate and leadership. The questionnaire consists of a total of 50 questions, established using a Likert scale from 1 to 5 points; represented as: never=1; almost never=2; sometimes=3; almost always=4; always=5, it is useful to describe that the items are distributed in nine dimensions, seven dimensions that evaluate the organizational climate and the remaining two, leadership.

Table 1: Dimensions

DIMENSIONS	Nº. ITEMS	CODING
Perception of boss/worker communication, in terms of the empathy and openness that the subordinate perceives from the superior.	7	(CJT)
Perception of the quality and accuracy of downward communication (from boss to workers).	8	(CEC)
Perception of upward communication, particularly the empathic and affective aspects of that relationship.	6	(CAP)
Perception of opportunities to influence the boss	5	(OIJ)
Perception of the reliability of the information received from the boss.	2	(CIRJ)
Perception of the reliability of information received from co-workers.	8	(CIRC)
Perception of communication between subordinates (level of affection, support, companionship, and openness).	4	(CES)
Leadership Level of information exchange.	7	(LNII)
Leadership Level of participation in decision-making.	3	(LNP)

Procedure

The process began with data collection, which included the design of a sociodemographic survey. Subsequently, the application instrument was incorporated using the Google Forms platform. In this context, the study guidelines were presented along with instructions for participants to communicate the purpose of the research. Additionally, informed consent was provided, ensuring that subjects could freely decide on their participation, under the ethical code and the Helsinki Declaration (Casas M., 2016).

Statistical analysis

This process was carried out by verifying the existence of missing data and then using the SPSS statistical program to process the data. First, a descriptive analysis of the data was performed: age, gender, type of employment relationship, and respondent profile. Subsequently, we proceeded to test the assumption of normality of the data using the Kolmogorov test to determine the distribution of the data. Next, a Spearman correlation analysis was applied to determine the association of the organisational climate and leadership variables, without neglecting the association of the variables

with their components; then, a multiple linear regression was performed, the dependent variable being leadership and the independent variable, the components of the organisational climate.

Results

According to the descriptive analysis, the main sociodemographic characteristics of the participants are identified. Gender: 50.4% of the respondents are female, while 49.6% are male. Regarding the type of employment relationship, 61.8% (551 participants) belong to special regimes, with 25.4% (227 participants) having an appointment, 10.3% (92 participants) having permanent contracts, 1.2% are under occasional contracts, and 2.5% (22 participants) are under occasional contracts.

This profile clearly shows the distribution of participants according to their employment relationship and gender, which facilitates understanding of the context in which the study is framed.

Table 2: Socio-demographic characteristics

Variable	Category	N	%
Genre	Male	442	49,6
	Female	450	50,4
Type of employment relationship	Permanent Contract	92	10,3
	Other special regimes	551	61,8
	Occasional Contracts	22	2,5
	Appointment	227	25,4
	Administrative	342	38,3
Respondent profile	Teacher	499	55,9
	Graduate Analyst 1	1	,1
	Academic Director	39	4,4
	Administrative Director	10	1,1
	Higher authority	1	,1
Relationship of hierarchy	Graduate Analyst 1	1	,1
	Subordinate	842	94,4
	Executives	50	5,6
Total		892	100

Table 2 shows the descriptive data based on the dimensions of the organizational climate and leadership study, showing the sum of each of the dimensions of the organizational climate: Perception of the quality and accuracy of downward communication - from the boss to the workers (CEC= 32,5484), Perception of the reliability of the information received from co-workers

(CIRC=32,5226), on the other hand in the leadership dimension stands out with a mean of Leadership Level of information exchange (LNII = 30,8135).

Table 3: Descriptive data

	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis	Minimum	Maximum
CJT	29,5475	32,0000	6,71720	45,121	-1,552	2,155	7,00	35,00
CEC	32,5484	34,0000	7,54011	56,853	-1,241	1,335	8,00	40,00
CAP	23,8270	24,0000	5,79250	33,553	-1,033	,639	6,00	30,00
OIJ	19,8456	20,0000	4,57283	20,911	-,791	,106	5,00	25,00
CIRJ	7,8195	8,0000	2,07773	4,317	-,866	,156	2,00	10,00
CIRC	32,5226	33,0000	6,66491	44,421	-,910	,594	8,00	40,00
CES	15,6722	16,0000	3,71127	13,774	-,873	,426	4,00	20,00
LNII	30,8135	31,0000	5,48175	30,050	-,480	,989	8,00	40,00
LNP	9,4774	9,0000	2,79291	7,800	,487	-,267	3,00	15,00
Totals								
Cl_Or	137,9630	142,0000	28,96562	839,007	-1,124	,990	34,00	170,00
Leadership	40,2910	40,0000	7,69883	59,272	-,015	,591	11,00	55,00

After the data description, a normality test was carried out to determine the distribution of the data to select the corresponding tests for the relationship between organisational climate and leadership. According to the results of the normality tests, it reflected a value of $p=,000$, which led to rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative. This implies that the variables to be studied do not have a normal distribution of the data. This type of procedure is relevant because it allows the selection of the necessary tests to perform a statistical analysis, as in the case of the correlation between organisational climate and leadership.

A Spearman correlation analysis was performed once the normality hypothesis test was carried out. This type of analysis allows the evaluation of the degree of association between variables, in this case, organisational climate and its components with leadership. According to the literature, the value must be close to 1 or -1 for an association to exist. According to some studies, those values above 0,70 indicate a strong positive correlation. (Cohen , 1988; Kuckartz, Rädiker , Ebert , & Schehl , 2013; Mondragón Barrera, 2014) According to the values of the results of the associations of the variables presented in Table 2: organisational climate and leadership, a value of Spearman's $Rho=0.69$ was obtained, $p=0.001$; both variables have a moderate positive association, according to Martínez González et al. (2020) in the literature.

Table 4: Spearman's Correlation of Leadership, Organisational Climate and its Components

Variable		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. CJT	Spearman's Rho	-										
	p-value	-										
2. CEC	Spearman's Rho	0.89	-									
	p-value	< .001	-									
3. CAP	Spearman's Rho	0.86	0.91	-								
	p-value	< .001	< .001	-								
4. OIJ	Spearman's Rho	0.74	0.76	0.84	-							
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	-							
5. CIRJ	Spearman's Rho	0.74	0.73	0.79	0.84	-						
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	-						
6. CIRC	Spearman's Rho	0.76	0.78	0.83	0.87	0.84	-					
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	-				
7. CES	Spearman's Rho	0.76	0.80	0.84	0.79	0.75	0.82	-				
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	-			
8. LNII	Spearman's Rho	0.64	0.66	0.73	0.75	0.71	0.77	0.77	-			
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	-		
9. LNP	Spearman's Rho	0.29	0.31	0.36	0.34	0.34	0.36	0.42	0.63	-		
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	-	
10. Cl_Or	Spearman's Rho	0.90	0.92	0.93	0.90	0.87	0.93	0.89	0.78	0.38	-	
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	-
11. Leadership	Spearman's Rho	0.57	0.59	0.65	0.66	0.63	0.68	0.71	0.96	0.82	0.69	-
	p-value	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001	< .001

Figure 1: Correlation Map, Spearman

Next, in figure 1, we proceeded to evaluate the reliability scores of the applied tests, so it was necessary to know the internal consistency of each of the 9 dimensions immersed in the study and general, so that, it was performed by the consistency method through a Cronbach's alpha and Omega's alpha of the instrument. (Acosta-Prado , Zarate Torres , & Tafur Mendoza, 2022; Viladrich, Angulo Brunet, & Doval, 2017) Tables 3 and 4, show the internal consistency through the scores explained through Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's alpha of each of the dimensions and items of the instrument, reflecting values between 0,786 and 0,986, according to some authors mention that a value > 0,70 are considered adequate values, this means that the instrument is reliable for application (Cronbach , 1951; Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994)

Table 5: Internal Consistency

Reliability statistics		
Cronbach's alpha	ω McDonald's	N of elements
,946	,953	9
,983	,986	50

Table 6: Internal Consistency

Dimension	Items	Cronbach's alpha	ω McDonald's
Organizational climate	40 items	0,986	0,986
CJT	7 items	0.948	0.953
CEC	8 items	0.972	0.972
CAP	6 items	0.939	0.943
OIJ	5 items	0.904	0.905
CIRJ	2 items	0.784	0.793
CIRC	8 items	0.929	0.931
CES	4 items	0.873	0.874
Leadership	10 items	0.807	0.868
LNII	7 items	0.786	0.877
LNP	3 items	0.797	0.797

Therefore, in table 5 and 6, a multiple regression is established to know the predictors of leadership, where the table shows the values of R, R-squared, adjusted R-squared, and the standard error of the estimation, each of the estimators allows evaluating the model adjustments, in turn explaining the variability of the data and the time of estimators with their predictors, where the dependent variable is leadership and its independent variables are the components of the organizational climate.

According to the results shown: Model 1, the R=,716, which shows a correlation of the model, the predictor CES shows an R-squared=,513, which represents 51.3% of the variability in the leadership variable. Similarly, in model 2, the R=,742 shows a moderate positive correlation, the increase of the predictors CES and CIRC gives an R-squared=,550 which represents 55% of the explanation of the data. According to the results presented; in model 3, the R=,746 shows a moderate positive correlation, the increase of the predictors CES, CIRC, and OIJ gives an R-squared=,557 which represents 55.7% of the explanation of the data.

Finally, model 4 shows a better model, where an R=,751 reflects a moderate positive correlation, and the increase of the predictors CES, CIRC, and OIJ results in an R-squared=,563, which represents 56.3 % of the explanation of the dependent variable is explained by the established predictors. It was shown that the CES predictor is one of the most relevant predictors in the organisational context.

Table 7: Model summary

Model	R	R-squared	Adjusted squared	R- Standard error of the estimate
1	,716 ^a	,513	,512	5,400
2	,742 ^b	,550	,549	5,193
3	,746 ^c	,557	,555	5,158
4	,751 ^d	,563	,561	5,122

a. Predictors: (Constant), CES
 b. Predictors: (Constant), CES, CIRC
 c. Predictors: (Constant), CES, CIRC, OIJ
 d. Predictors: (Constant), CES, CIRC, OIJ, CJT
 e. Dependent variable: Leadership

Note: *Predictors: perception of the quality and accuracy of downward communication (from boss to workers (CES); perception of the reliability of information received from co-workers (CIRC); perception of opportunities to influence the boss (OIJ) and perception of boss/workers communication, in terms of empathy and openness perceived by the subordinate from the superior (CJT). Dependent variable; Leadership.*

The following ANOVA table shows the explanation of each of the models in a significant proportion of the variance explained concerning the dependent variable, leadership. Each of the models was significant, which means that by adding each of the predictors, they show a better global adjustment and that of each one of them.

Table 8: ANOVA results

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of squares	gl	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27187,655	1	27187,655	932,320	,000 ^b
	Error	25807,749	885	29,161		
	Total	52995,405	886			
2	Regression	29151,796	2	14575,898	540,400	,000 ^c
	Error	23843,609	884	26,972		
	Total	52995,405	886			
3	Regression	29507,530	3	9835,843	369,767	,000 ^d
	Error	23487,875	883	26,600		
	Total	52995,405	886			

4	Regressio n	29854,733	4	7463,683	284,476	,000 ^e
	Error	23140,671	882	26,237		
	Total	52995,405	886			

a. Dependent variable: Leadership
 b. Predictors: (Constant), CES
 c. Predictors: (Constant), CES, CIRC
 d. Predictors: (Constant), CES, CIRC, OIJ
 e. Predictors: (Constant), CES, CIRC, OIJ, CJT

The following table shows the four models, with the unstandardized (B) and standardized (beta) coefficients, t-values, and respective significance. Thus, the stepwise method was established, which allows for selecting the optimal model. According to the results, model 4: The CES predictor has a coefficient beta=0.429 with a significance level of p=0.000, so this factor is a strong predictor compared to the others. The CIRC has a beta of 0.292 with a p of 0.000. The OIJ shows a beta=0.190, indicating a significant p. Finally, the CJT reflects a beta=-0.142, which has a p=0.000 value.

Table 9: Multiple regression results
Coefficients^a

Model		Non-standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients		
		B	Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	16,874	,795		21,216	,000
	CES	1,504	,049	,716	30,534	,000
2	(Constant)	13,144	,881		14,919	,000
	CES	,880	,087	,419	10,104	,000
	CIRC	,415	,049	,354	8,533	,000
3	(Constant)	13,072	,875		14,937	,000
	CES	,793	,090	,378	8,840	,000
	CIRC	,273	,062	,233	4,395	,000
	OIJ	,305	,083	,178	3,657	,000
4	(Constant)	13,611	,882		15,437	,000
	CES	,901	,094	,429	9,593	,000
	CIRC	,343	,065	,292	5,307	,000
	OIJ	,327	,083	,190	3,931	,000
	CJT	-,166	,046	-,142	-3,638	,000

a. Dependent variable: Leadership

The analysis of the coefficient table reveals how different components of organizational climate influence leadership, using a multiple regression model. In the first model, the CES component (communication between boss and subordinate) shows an unstandardized coefficient of 1.504,

indicating a positive and significant effect on leadership, with a high t-value (30.534) and a high statistical significance level ($p < 0.001$).

In the second model, when the CIRC component (trust in information from peers) is included, the impact of CES decreases to 0.880, although it is still significant. CIRC, on the other hand, shows an unstandardized coefficient of 0.415 and a standardized coefficient of 0.354, which implies a significant positive effect on leadership ($t = 8.533$, $p < 0.001$).

The third model introduces the OIJ component (opportunity to influence superiors), which slightly reduces the coefficients of CES (0.793) and CIRC (0.273), but these remain significant. OIJ has a standardized coefficient of 0.178, reflecting a moderate positive influence on leadership ($t = 3.657$, $p < 0.001$).

Finally, the fourth model adds the CJT component (perceived communication with the boss), which presents a negative coefficient (-0.166), indicating that this factor has an inverse impact on leadership. Despite this negative influence, the coefficients of CES (0.901), CIRC (0.343) and OIJ (0.327) continue to show positive and significant effects.

Overall, CES remains the strongest factor in all models, followed by CIRC and OIJ, while CJT has a negative impact on leadership. These results highlight the importance of effective and reliable communication between superiors and colleagues to promote effective leadership within the organisation, as shown in Table 9.

Discussion

This study on the influence of organisational climate on leadership in higher education institutions is crucial in the current context, where the quality of the work environment directly influences academic and administrative performance. The findings corroborate the hypothesis that a positive organisational climate favours leadership effectiveness and contributes to the integral development of employees, thus improving educational and administrative quality. This relationship is fundamental for the management of institutions since a good work climate translates into greater satisfaction and commitment, key elements for institutional success (Brito-Carrillo et al., 2020).

However, this study has certain limitations. First, the cross-sectional nature of the research design precludes establishing definitive causal relationships between variables. In addition, using a non-probabilistic sample could limit the generalizability of the results to other higher education institutions. The homogeneity of the sample in terms of gender and type of employment relationship could also influence the diversity of perceptions of organisational climate and leadership.

Comparing our results with previous studies, we observe an alignment with existing literature highlighting the interrelationship between organizational climate and transformational leadership (Ko et al., 2019; Lockstone-Binney et al., 2019). However, transactional leadership, while effective in specific contexts, has been found to fail to foster a motivating and creative work environment in the long term. This reinforces the need to prioritize transformational leadership in educational settings, where innovation and adaptability are essential.

For future research, longitudinal designs are recommended to explore the evolution of the relationships between organizational climate and leadership over time. In addition, they would include greater diversity in the sample, considering different types of institutions and geographical contexts. Likewise, including mediating variables, such as organisational communication and professional development, could provide a deeper understanding of how climate and leadership are interrelated.

Finally, higher education institutions are suggested to implement leadership development programs that focus on transformational practices, fostering a positive organisational climate. This will improve job satisfaction and enhance employee commitment to institutional goals, contributing to continuous improvement in educational quality. Attention to the factors that influence the organisational climate is crucial for the development of healthy and productive work environments, thus facilitating the achievement of strategic goals in the educational field.

Conclusion

The conclusion of this study highlights the critical importance of the relationship between organisational climate and leadership in higher education institutions. Through a detailed quantitative analysis, it became evident that a positive organisational climate not only enhances leadership effectiveness but also contributes to the integral development of employees, directly impacting educational and administrative quality. The findings suggest that improving the work environment can increase employee satisfaction and performance, resulting in better academic results.

However, it is essential to recognise the study's limitations, such as its cross-sectional design and the homogeneity of the sample, which could affect the generalizability of the results. Despite this, the results are consistent with the existing literature, highlighting the interrelationship between organisational climate and transformational leadership. This reinforces the need to prioritise leadership approaches that foster innovation and adaptability, essential in the educational setting.

For future research, it is recommended to adopt longitudinal designs, diversify the samples, and include mediating variables that enrich the understanding of this relationship. Consequently, it is suggested that institutions implement leadership development programs focused on transformational practices. These programs will not only improve the organisational climate but also strengthen employee commitment to institutional objectives, thus facilitating the achievement of strategic goals. Attention to these factors is vital for developing healthy and productive work environments, contributing to the continuous advancement of educational quality.

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